

ANNUAL REPORT 2024

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US Research Software Engineer Association (US-RSE)

<https://us-rse.org>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This has been a year of extraordinary change and growth for the US Research Software Engineer Association (US-RSE)¹, a grassroots organization built by and for the research software engineer community. Our progress this year would not have been possible without the passion, dedication, and collaborative spirit of our members. Thanks to the support of the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, we had crucial funding that has allowed us to invest in dedicated staff and expand our programs significantly. This strategic investment, combined with the enthusiastic commitment of our community, has driven a 27% increase in our membership, bringing together a diverse and talented community of RSEs.

Our strengthened capacity has enabled us to launch impactful new initiatives, such as the community funds and enabled us to intensify our outreach to a diverse community and different stakeholders. These efforts have fostered a vibrant and connected community, providing valuable opportunities for professional development and knowledge sharing.

Beyond community building, we have amplified our advocacy efforts, raising awareness among key stakeholders, including funding agencies and policymakers, about the indispensable role RSEs play in advancing research. This increased recognition is essential for securing support and resources that empower RSEs to continue their critical work.

As we look to the future, the US-RSE is committed to further expanding our programs, with a particular focus on delivering high-quality professional development resources and advocating for policies that champion the RSE profession. We are deeply grateful to our members, volunteers, partners, and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation for their invaluable contributions to this year's successes. Together, we are building a thriving RSE ecosystem that drives innovation and strengthens the foundation of scientific discovery.

¹ US-RSE is a fiscally sponsored project of Community Initiatives.

LETTER FROM THE EXECUTIVE DIRECTOR

Dear US-RSE Members and Allies,

As this year ends, I'm filled with gratitude and pride for the incredible progress our vibrant US-RSE community has made. With over 3,000 members and the success of our second in-person US-RSE conference, we have strengthened our space for collaboration, knowledge sharing, and mutual support. This event highlighted the power of a community where individuals from diverse career paths and backgrounds come together with a shared sense of purpose.

This year brought many key milestones. Continued funding from the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation has been important in solidifying our operational foundation. The launch of our Organizational Membership Program is an exciting step toward financial sustainability, fostering deeper partnerships and expanding recognition for RSEs within the research ecosystem.

Reflecting on the past year, the uncharted waters I faced as your Executive Director no longer feel so unknown, thanks to the incredible support of this community. I want to express my heartfelt gratitude to the Steering Committee, whose dedication and hands-on contributions have been crucial to our growth and success. I'm equally thankful for the strong support of our members, my advisory board, and mentors, whose guidance and encouragement have made this journey possible.

Looking ahead, advocacy, funding, and the sustainability of US-RSE remain focal points of my work. The Steering Committee and I are committed to advancing professional development, career recognition, and innovative programs for both current and future RSEs. Globally, US-RSE continues to strengthen ties with international RSE communities, reminding us that we are part of a worldwide movement to elevate the visibility and impact of RSEs. Together, we are stronger.

As we enter the holiday season, I hope you find time to rest, recharge, and celebrate. Thank you for being part of this extraordinary journey—I'm always grateful for your ideas and input, so please don't hesitate to reach out.

Wishing you a joyful holiday season and a happy, healthy New Year!

Warm regards,

Sandra Gesing
Executive Director, US-RSE

MISSION, VISION AND GOALS

US-RSE is the leading professional community of research software engineering practitioners in the United States. US-RSE's four-pronged mission aims to foster community, promote RSEs' impact on research, provide useful resources, and encourage and improve diversity throughout the profession. US-RSE envisions a future where it plays an essential role in promoting RSEs to be universally respected for advancing science, technology, and society through the transformative power of research software engineering.

Goals for the next 5 years

US-RSE aims to expand its impact by increasing membership, enhancing diversity, and fostering professional growth. Goals include growing membership to 7,000 in five years, supported by outreach to academia, national labs, and industry. Efforts to increase diversity focus on partnerships with Minority Serving Institutions and organizations like the Association of Computer Science Departments at Minority Institutions. To enhance professional development, the association plans to launch mentorship and leadership programs. Additionally, US-RSE seeks to build active local chapters and refine programs through annual member surveys.

Financial sustainability is a critical priority, with a goal to secure sufficient funding for staff salaries and community activities within two years. Organizational memberships will support this aim. Advocacy efforts include applying for awards and conducting a nationwide awareness campaign on the value of research software engineering.

Steering Committee 2024

MEMBERSHIP AND COMMUNITY

It is very exciting that we reached the milestone of over 3000 individual members In 2024.

Our community thrives through a variety of activities designed to engage and support members. Monthly community calls and newsletters keep members informed and connected, while 15 active working groups and affinity groups foster collaboration on specialized topics. Virtual seminar series, such as the Education and Training Speaker Series, provide valuable opportunities for learning and discussion. The community also benefits from a highly visited and successful job board, as well as the creation of impactful resources, including the 100-page Career Guidebook developed in collaboration with the Academic Data Science Alliance and the 25-page Career Guide Brochure for RSEs produced with the IEEE Computer Society. These initiatives collectively strengthen the community and advance the field of research software engineering.

ORGANIZATIONAL MEMBERSHIP

The pilot phase for organizational founding members gives organizations the opportunity to be recognized in perpetuity as founding members of US-RSE. Every organization joining on or before November 30, 2025 will be considered an organizational founding member. The annual membership fees will remain the same for founding members until December 31, 2028. Organizations joining on or after December 1, 2025 are ineligible to become an organizational founding member.

Contact our Executive Director Sandra Gesing if you are interested!

Current founding members

Premier level

Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory is in the process of joining!

Standard level

Globus is in the process of joining!

ANNUAL CONFERENCE

Our second conference at the Albuquerque Convention Center was a tremendous success, bringing together 275 participants for lively discussions and knowledge exchange. The program showcased an impressive range of submissions, including Birds of a Feather (BoFs), workshops, tutorials, papers, notebooks, posters, and talks, complemented by engaging additional features. Highlights included two inspiring keynotes, a student program, sponsor talks, Rapid Access Microtalks, a poster reception and poster awards, a memorable conference dinner, and a post-conference visit to the Nuclear History Museum. The event also featured the announcement of the Better Scientific Software Fellowship, further solidifying the conference as a hub for innovation and collaboration.

Travel with us and our mascot, the unicorn, to Philadelphia in 2025!

PROGRAMS AND INITIATIVES

The Community and Travel Funds program is a key initiative supporting the growth and development of the US-RSE community. With grants ranging from \$100 to \$10,000 (typically up to \$2,500), the program funds activities such as local RSE events, training sessions, conference participation, professional development, and outreach efforts. Applications are evaluated quarterly based on community impact, alignment with US-RSE's mission, and the applicants' qualifications and engagement. Funded recipients share their experiences through brief reports, fostering knowledge-sharing and inspiration within the community.

The US-RSE Community Awards recognize individuals who have made outstanding contributions to the RSE community. The Excellence in Service Award honors exceptional dedication to US-RSE's mission, while the Impact Award highlights significant advancements in the RSE profession, such as education, visibility, and community growth. Winners receive recognition, a certificate, and a monetary gift.

Christina Maimone received the Excellence in Service Award and Dan S. Katz received the Impact Award in 2024.

In 2024, we showcased the diversity of the US-RSE community by publishing member spotlights on LinkedIn, highlighting their unique contributions and stories.

ADVOCACY

US-RSE is dedicated to advancing the recognition and support of RSEs as critical contributors to modern research and innovation. Through outreach to funding bodies such as the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, the National Science Foundation (NSF), and the Department of Energy (DOE), US-RSE advocates for the professional growth, visibility, and sustainability of RSEs across disciplines.

With a focus on community-building activities, career resources, and partnerships with leading institutions, US-RSE strengthens the RSE profession and fosters collaboration among researchers, software engineers, and policymakers. Sandra Gesing travels nationwide and internationally to engage with stakeholders, present at conferences, and represent the association in discussions with funding agencies and research institutions. These efforts aim to enhance the integration of RSEs in the research ecosystem, promote diversity and inclusion, and secure resources to support their essential contributions to scientific and engineering advancements.

In 2024, Sandra Gesing delivered 29 presentations, including talks, keynotes, and panel contributions. US-RSE had a booth and social events at the PEARC24, SC24 and AGU24 conferences.

FINANCIAL REPORT

US-RSE has experienced significant financial activity, supported primarily by the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation grant, by the National Science Foundation travel support, organizational memberships, and conference sponsors. The Sloan grant, awarded in Spring 2023, provides approximately \$400,000 annually for two years, with the second installment received in Spring 2024. Additional income includes \$24,000 from organizational memberships and \$470 from individual donations. Major spending categories include salaries for the Executive Director and Community Manager, staff travel for outreach, conference and activity funding, code of conduct training, and assorted smaller expenses. Administrative costs, including a 10% CI fee (minimum \$2,500 per year), are also accounted for.

The annual US-RSE conference continues to be a key financial focus, with ~\$93,000 generated from registrations and ~\$72,000 from sponsorships, against expenses totaling ~\$200,000. While registration fees were \$400-\$450 for regular attendees and \$100-\$150 for students, these may need to increase in future years to ensure sustainability. Sloan funding facilitated upfront costs like venue deposits, while revenue from past conferences will support future events, including US-RSE'25. Budget plans for the upcoming year prioritize salaries, expanded member activities, outreach-related travel, and conference preparations, alongside smaller investments in membership management software and branded outreach materials. These efforts aim to secure the long-term success and growth of the US-RSE community and its initiatives.

“Magical Unicorn” Fundraiser 2024

Our unicorns are not really growing on trees – they are ready to travel to you though!

Regular Donation to US-RSE

PARTNERS AND SPONSORS

We extend our deepest gratitude to our partners, organizational members (page 7) and sponsors for their invaluable support and collaboration. Your contributions have played a major role in advancing our mission to elevate the visibility and impact of RSEs. From funding critical initiatives to fostering partnerships that expand resources and opportunities for our community, your commitment has been a major contribution in our growth and success. Together, we have achieved significant milestones, strengthened the RSE profession, and laid a foundation for future advancements. We look forward to building on our successes and exploring new opportunities for collaboration in the years ahead.

We would like to especially thank the following partners: Academic Data Science Alliance (ADSA), Agile Alliance, Better Scientific Software (BSSw), Coalition for Academic Scientific Computation (CASC) and Research Software Alliance (ReSA).

The conference sponsors are crucial to make our conference a success!

Diamond

Travel funding

Platinum

Gold

Silver

Bronze

Photography Sponsor

Event Sponsor

LOOKING AHEAD

As we move forward, US-RSE remains focused on expanding its impact and ensuring the long-term sustainability of our organization. Building on the progress made this year, we aim to leverage a no-cost extension from the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation as well as additional funding while exploring opportunities for federal grants, foundational support and funding through new leads provided by our work with RBW Strategy. Strengthening advocacy efforts with funding bodies and fostering partnerships with organizations like the U.S. Department of Labor will remain key priorities. Additionally, we plan to host a focus group with industry leaders to better understand their needs and strengthen ties. Expanding Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) with like-minded projects and initiatives will also help solidify our collaborations. To enhance strategic alignment, we will establish regular quarterly meetings with leaders of non-traditional organizations such as the Academic Data Science Alliance (ADSA), CASC (Coalition for Academic Scientific Computations), The Carpentries, ReSA (Research Software Alliance) and other RSE associations to share knowledge and amplify collective efforts.

Internally, US-RSE will prioritize outreach and operational sustainability. Filling the Community Manager position is beneficial to supporting our vibrant working groups, affinity groups, regional groups, and conference committees. We will ensure our activities align with our mission, focusing on sustaining key platforms like the job board, mentorship initiatives, and the annual US-RSE conference—our flagship event. As we continue to empower RSEs through support and opportunities, our goal is to maintain an engaged, thriving community while expanding the recognition and visibility of research software engineering across the broader research ecosystem.

Call for Action

The US-RSE community is thriving, and we need *you* to keep the momentum going! From Slack conversations to working groups, community calls, and conferences, our members are driving the RSE movement forward. Whether you're answering questions, sharing resources, or starting new initiatives, your contributions make this community inviting, inclusive, and impactful. Are you wondering if you can post in Slack? Yes! Create a channel? Yes! Start an initiative or join a working group? Absolutely! No matter your sector—HPC, national labs, universities, or beyond—there's a place for you here. Join us, connect with fellow RSEs, and help sustain this growing movement. Together, we're shaping the future of research software engineering!

As one member shared, "*The best part of the US-RSE is the community of active and friendly individuals who are always willing to help their fellow members.*" Another added, "*Everyone is so supportive! Every question in Slack gets at least one useful answer, and folks are constantly sharing ideas and resources.*" Let's keep building this incredible community together!